
ABSTRACT

Commercialized flight simulators are considered as a training tool for aircrafts, validated by pilots of real systems. The aerodynamic aspect of aircrafts existing on the libraries of these simulators is treated in a shallow way. For example, the Microsoft Flight Simulator 2004 (MSFS 2004), which is used in this work, uses the file "aircraft.cfg" of the folder "Flight Simulator 9" to stock some values that will be multiplied by the aerodynamic coefficients derivatives that are considered unknown and vary in time.

These aerodynamic coefficients are important in the evaluation of the aircraft performance and stability-control characteristics. These coefficients also can be used in the automatic flight control systems and mathematical model of flight simulator.

The Microsoft Flight Simulator has APIs, developed by Microsoft and third party programmers, which allow integration of new "add-ons" and external software and hardware modules.

In this paper, we propose to present the integration of an aircraft's (F-16) virtual model in the Microsoft Flight Simulator FS-2004, and the procedure of identifying its aerodynamic coefficients.

KEYWORDS: Aerodynamic coefficients, Aircraft's (F-16) virtual model, 3D modeling and Integration, Gmax tool, Microsoft flight simulator, Total least squares estimator, Virtual model reality .

INTRODUCTION

The study of the aerodynamic aspect of flying systems is a reserved domain and inaccessible for the developers. Doing tests in a wind tunnel to extract aerodynamic forces and moments requires a specific and expensive means. Besides, the glaring lack of published documentation in this field of study makes the aerodynamic coefficients determination complicated.

In order to develop better approaches of aircraft aerodynamic effects' modeling, flight validation of the models will be essential. This could effectively be accomplished, in a first step, by using flight simulators.

In this paper, we propose to present the integration of an aircraft's (F-16) virtual model in the Microsoft Flight Simulator FS-2004, and the procedure of identifying its aerodynamic coefficients.

For the integration part, a 3D aircraft model F-16 is created and modeled by using the gmax tool. Thereafter, this model is exported to the simulated environment, then; its dynamic characteristics are injected by programming the model's configuration file "aircraft.cfg" located in FS-2004 installation folder.

For the identification part, we estimate the aerodynamic coefficients using the Total Least Square Estimators (TLSE) method.

MICROSOFT FLIGHT SIMULATOR (MSFS)

Introduction

Microsoft Flight Simulator (MSFS) is a software marketed by MicrosoftTM since 1982, when its first version "Sublogic" made by Bruce Artwick appeared. Since then, it had known a big development in its dynamic and graphic modeling. Indeed, the latest versions: Century of Flight (FS2004) and Flight Simulator X (FSX) appeared in 2003 and 2006 respectively, are considered more as an immersive virtual environment dedicated to pilots training rather than video games.

MSFS implements real-time model [1] using the parametric approach which is based on a set of tabulated parameters (weight, number of engines, their type, the wing surface, inertia...) [2]. We chose MSFS2004 for the following reasons:

- The frame time is sufficiently small, so we notice that the simulation in MSFS is in real time [1], [3];
- The FS2004 offers sufficient quality of graphical modeling [2], [4];
- The FS2004 is not greedy in computational resources compared to other COTS-FS of the same category (FSX, Xplane ...) [3]. Moreover, it is considered as low-cost;
- The FS2004 library is extensible by adding and customizing airplanes, scenery, sounds and flight instruments [4], [12];
- In addition to the internal aspects, FS2004 has APIs, developed by Microsoft and third party programmers, which allow integration of new “add-ons” and external software and hardware modules [2].

The Internet sees growth of a market that meets the needs of users by offering a multitude of software and hardware solutions. This is a very important advantage for MSFS, as it promotes not only the availability of software and hardware, but also knowledge, techniques and experiences that avoid a heavy development. Most of these “add-ons” are based on Peter Dowson’s API: FSUIPC (Flight Simulator Universal Inter-Process Communication), which allows communication with FS2004 in real-time [5]. [16].

The Aircraft Configuration File “*.cfg”

The Aircraft Container system organizes Flight Simulator 2004 aircraft files and attributes so that most aircraft-related files are located together. This logical and consistent organization makes the files easy to customize.

The “SDK FS2004” (Software Development Kit) describes the aircraft container system in detail, explaining how the different files work together. It provides information on how to modify and share components among existing aircraft. It does not explain how to create new aircraft.

The “aircraft.cfg” is the configuration file for the aircraft. It is easily editable and the most important file for the user in that respect. The structure of this file is as follows:

- It contains a text block of information which is directly related to aircraft behavior and contains data (external parameters) for the flight dynamics, in addition to those in the “.air file” (internal parameters);
- It contains a second block with information about all the liveries of that aircraft type.

An example of such a text block for the “MQ-1 Predator” looks as follows (see: C:\Program Files \ Microsoft Games \ Flight Simulator9 \ VIPER \ Aircraft \).

Table 1. Sections file.cfg

Section [fltsim.0]	
Title	= VIPER gbu
Sim	= VIPER
Model	= GBU
atc_id	=94
atc_id_color	=0x00ffffff
Section [General]	
atc_type	= LOCKHEED
atc_model	= F16
Editable	=1
performance	= maximum level speed Mach 2.0 at 12190 m (40,000ft) > service ceiling above 15240 m (50,000 feet) > operational radius 925 km (575 miles) > empty 7070 kg (15,586 lb) > maximum take-off 16,057 kg (35,400 lb)
[Weight and Balance]	
max_gross_weight	= 32211.000
empty_weight	= 10000.000 // (pounds)

The [flight_tuning] section

The [flight_tuning] section is reserved for the aircraft aerodynamic model. We note that in many cases all parameters are set to 1.0 as the default value. These values are multiplied by the aerodynamic coefficients which are unknown.

The following table shows an example of the [flight_tuning] section in the aircraft.cfg [6]:

Table 2. Section “Flight tuning” in file.cfg

[flight_tuning]		
Property	Description	Value
cruise_lift_scalar	C_{L0}	= 1.000
parasite_drag_scalar	C_{D0}	= 1.000
induced_drag_scalar	C_{Di}	= 1.000
elevator_effectiveness	$C_{m\delta e}$	= 1.000
aileron_effectiveness	$C_{L\delta a}$	= 1.000
rudder_effectiveness	$C_{n\delta r}$	= 1.000
pitch_stability	C_{mq}	= 1.000
roll_stability	C_{Lp}	= 1.000
yaw_stability	C_{nr}	= 1.000
elevator_trim_effectiveness	$C_{m\delta e}$	= 1.000
aileron_trim_effectiveness	$C_{L\delta r}$	= 1.000
rudder_trim_effectiveness	$C_{n\delta r}$	= 1.000

INTEGRATION PART

Through a methodology based on the confrontation of the real and the simulated worlds, the main objective of the present work is to develop an aircraft’s virtual model. To achieve this objective, we use the Microsoft Flight Simulator FS2004 as a simulated world environment coupled to a hardware and a software development platform. We choose the F-16 aircraft because its aerodynamic aspect is treated in [7] and [14] by using the tests of wind tunnel. We use the gmax tool to create, 3D modulate and integrate an F-16 virtual model in the Microsoft Flight Simulator environment, then we use the aerodynamic characteristics treated in [7] and [14] to configure our model’s dynamic by programming the model's configuration file “aircraft.cfg” located in FS-2004 installation folder.

In this work, we propose the following approach:

- Creation and 3D modeling of the aircraft by using the gmax tool;
- Export the model “aircraft.gmax” to FS2004 to obtain “aircraft.mdl” model by using the "makemdl" compiler (this "aircraft.mdl" file must be placed in” C:\Program Files \ Microsoft Games \ Flight Simulator9 \ Aircraft \ F-16\ model” directory);
- Programming the dynamic model of the F-16 system by editing the “aircraft.cfg” file ;
- Implementation of a real time interface between the flight simulator FS2004 and the module real time Windows target of Simulink/Matlab;
- Procedure of identifying its aerodynamic coefficients;
- Flight tests.

Creation and 3d modeling of the aircraft by using GMax tool

Gmax is a freeware 3D editor created by former Discreet (now Autodesk). Although based on the 3ds max application, it is made specifically for developers. Gmax's utility can be expanded by "game packs" which feature customized tools that allow creation and exporting of the “models.gmax” to Microsoft flight simulator.

The Gmax tool is downloadable from the official discreet website www.turbosquid.com/gmax .

The created and 3D modeled aircraft F-16 is presented in the following figure.

Figure 1:

Model system "F-16.gmax".

The "FS2004 SDK Pack" is easily downloadable and contains many executable files such as "fs2004_sdk_gmax_setup.exe" and "makemdl_sdk_setup.exe" that provide the possibility of compiling a "gmax" file to an FS-2004 exploitable "mdl" file.

The gmax SDK (Software Development Kit) contains five separated SDKs, bundled together in one downloadable and installable file. When we install the "fs2004_sdk_gmax_setup.exe" in the gmax installation folder, we get the following tools and documentation: gmax_AttachTool, gmax_Animation, gmax_CloudTool, gmax_Aircraft and gmax_Scenery.

Once the "gmax gamepack SDK" is installed the created model can be exported to flight simulator by selecting "Flightsim aircraft object (*.MDL)" type when exporting.

System's dynamic model

The aircraft aerodynamic model identification is treated in [7] and [14] by using the wind tunnel (see figure 2). The derivative aerodynamic coefficients obtained in [7] and [14] are used to validate our aircraft model F-16.

Figure 2:

Photograph of 0.1 O-scale F-16 mounted for large amplitude pitching tests in wind tunnel [7] and [14].

The “SDK FS2004” (Software Development Kit) describes with details the aircraft container system, explaining how the different files work together. It provides information on how to modify and share components among existing aircraft. It does not explain how to create a new aircraft.

The “aircraft.cfg” is the configuration file for the aircraft. It is easily editable and the most important file for the user. The structure of this file is as follows:

- It contains a text block of information which is directly related to aircraft behavior and contains data (external parameters) for the flight dynamics, in addition to those in the “*.air” file (internal parameters);
- It contains a second block with information about all the liveries of that aircraft type.

Figure 3:

Exported aircraft F-16 flying in FS-2004.

IDENTIFICATION PROCEDURE PART

Structuring the Aerodynamic Data Base Aerodynamic Models

The aerodynamic data are expressed in terms of three forces (drag X , lift Z , side force Y) and three moments (pitching moment M , rolling moment L , yawing moment N) that act on the aircraft. Next, the effect of dynamic pressure and aircraft size (expressed in terms of wing area, and mean aerodynamic chord or wing span) is eliminated through working with dimensionless aerodynamic forces and moments coefficients [8], [13], [9], [5],[10].

$$C_x = \frac{X}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 S}, C_z = \frac{Z}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 S}, C_y = \frac{Y}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 S} \quad (1)$$

$$C_l = \frac{L}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 S b}, C_m = \frac{M}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 S \bar{c}}, C_n = \frac{N}{\frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 S b} \quad (2)$$

where; V : true air speed m/s , ρ : air density Kg/m^3 .

The aerodynamic coefficients $C_x \dots C_n$, in (1) and (2) are functions of the time histories of the aircraft state, i.e. angle-of-attack α , angle-of-sideslip β , the aircraft rotation rates p, q, r as well as the control surface deflections $\delta_e, \delta_a, \delta_r$. The functional relationship between the aerodynamic coefficients and the state variables are expressed in terms of Taylor's series expansions about a reference state. A representative example is [5], [9], [10],[11], [13], [18]:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 C_X = C_{X_0} + C_{X_\alpha} \alpha + C_{X_{\alpha^2}} \alpha^2 + C_{X_q} \frac{qc}{V} + C_{X_{\delta_e}} \delta_e + C_{X_{F_p}} F_p \\
 C_Y = C_{Y_0} + C_{Y\beta} \beta + C_{Y_p} \frac{pb}{2V} + C_{Y_r} \frac{rb}{2V} + C_{Y_{\delta_a}} \delta_a + C_{Y_{\delta_r}} \delta_r + C_{Y_{F_p}} \beta F_p \\
 C_Z = C_{Z_0} + C_{Z_\alpha} \alpha + C_{Z_q} \frac{qc}{V} + C_{Z_{\delta_e}} \delta_e + C_{Z_{\alpha F_p}} \alpha F_p \\
 C_l = C_{l_0} + C_{l\beta} \beta + C_{l_p} \frac{pb}{2V} + C_{l_r} \frac{rb}{2V} + C_{l_{\delta_a}} \delta_a + C_{l_{\delta_r}} \delta_r + C_{l_{F_p}} \delta_l F_p \\
 C_m = C_{m_0} + C_{m_\alpha} \alpha + C_{m_q} \frac{qc}{V} + C_{m_{\delta_e}} \delta_e + C_{m_{\alpha F_p}} \alpha F_p \\
 C_n = C_{n_0} + C_{n\beta} \beta + C_{n_p} \frac{pb}{2V} + C_{n_r} \frac{rb}{2V} + C_{n_{\delta_a}} \delta_a + C_{n_{\delta_r}} \delta_r + C_{n_{F_p}} \delta F_p
 \end{array} \right. \quad (3)$$

where,

$$C_{Z_\alpha} = \frac{\partial C_Z}{\partial \alpha}, C_{Y\beta} = \frac{\partial C_Y}{\partial \beta}, \quad \delta_l = (y_{cg} - y_{jet}), \quad \delta = (z_{cg} - z_{jet})$$

x_{jet} , y_{jet} and z_{jet} are the positions of the specific force sensors.

Table 3. Aerodynamic coefficients

Aerodynamic coefficient	Description
C_X :	Axial force coefficient (body frame)
C_{X0} :	Drag at zero angle of attack and sideslip
$C_{X\alpha}$:	Drag due to the angle of attack. Angle of attack will increase the area facing the wind and therefore increase the drag
C_Y :	Side force (body frame)
$C_{Y\beta}$:	Cross-wind force due to the sideslip. Sideslip will expose one side of the fuselage to the wind causing a net force in the Y direction
C_Z :	Normal force coefficient (body frame)
C_{Z0} :	Lift at zero angle of attack. This will be non-zero for asymmetric airfoils
$C_{Z\alpha}$:	Lift due to the increased angle of attack. The airfoil will generate greater lift as the angle of attack increases until the wing stalls
C_l, C_m, C_n	Roll, pitch, yaw moment coefficients;
C_{l_p} :	Damping from angular velocity. Mainly caused by the main wing when rolling
$C_{l_{\delta_a}}$:	Roll moment due to aileron control surface deflection
C_{l_β} :	Restoring roll moment due to the sideslip. Mainly caused by the dihedral angle of the wing and the vertical stabilizer
C_{m_α} :	Restoring pitch moment due to the angle of attack. The tail horizontal surface will be the main contributor to this moment as it will hit the wind with an angle and thus generate the restoring moment
C_{m_q} :	Damping from angular velocity. Mainly caused by the vertical stabilizer when yawing
$C_{m_{\delta_e}}$:	Pitch moment due to the elevator surface deflection
$C_{n\beta}$:	Pitch damping coefficient
C_{nr} :	Restoring yaw moment due to the side slip. Vertical stabilizer at the tail will generate a restoring moment because of the exposed area while side slipping
$C_{n_{\delta_r}}$:	Yaw moment due to the rudder control surface deflection

There is a verification model that matches the aerodynamic coefficients to the measurements provided by the sensors of the aircraft.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{m(a_x \cos \alpha \cos \beta + a_y \sin \beta + a_z \sin \alpha \cos \beta) - F_p \cos \alpha_m \cos \beta_m}{\frac{1}{2} \rho S V^2} = \\
 & C_{x_0} + C_{x_\alpha} \alpha + C_{x_{\alpha^2}} \alpha^2 + C_{x_q} \frac{q\bar{c}}{V} + C_{x_{\delta_e}} \delta_e \\
 & \frac{m(-a_x \sin \alpha + a_z \cos \alpha) - F_p \sin \alpha_m}{\frac{1}{2} \rho S V^2} = C_{z_0} + C_{z_\alpha} \alpha + C_{z_q} \frac{q\bar{c}}{V} + C_{z_{\delta_e}} \delta_e \\
 & \frac{m(-a_x \cos \alpha \sin \beta + a_y \cos \beta - a_z \sin \alpha \sin \beta) + F_p \cos \alpha_m \sin \beta_m}{\frac{1}{2} \rho S V^2} = \\
 & C_{y_0} + C_{y_\beta} \beta + C_{y_p} \frac{pb}{2V} + C_{y_r} \frac{rb}{2V} + C_{y_{\delta_a}} \delta_a + C_{y_{\delta_r}} \delta_r \\
 & \frac{\dot{p}I_{xx} + q.p(I_{zz} - I_{yy}) - (p.q + \dot{r})I_{xz}}{\frac{1}{2} \rho S b V^2} = \\
 & C_{l_0} + C_{l_\beta} \beta + C_{l_p} \frac{pb}{2V} + C_{l_r} \frac{rb}{2V} + C_{l_{\delta_a}} \delta_a + C_{l_{\delta_r}} \delta_r \\
 & \frac{\dot{q}I_{yy} + r.p(I_{xx} - I_{zz}) + (p^2 - r^2)I_{xz} - \Delta F_p}{\frac{1}{2} \rho S \bar{c} V^2} \\
 & = C_{m_0} + C_{m_\alpha} \alpha + C_{m_q} \frac{q\bar{c}}{V} + C_{m_{\delta_e}} \delta_e \\
 & \frac{\dot{r}I_{zz} + q.p(I_{yy} - I_{xx}) + (r.q - \dot{p})I_{xz}}{\frac{1}{2} \rho S b V^2} \\
 & = C_{n_0} + C_{n_\beta} \beta + C_{n_p} \frac{pb}{2V} + C_{n_r} \frac{rb}{2V} + C_{n_{\delta_a}} \delta_a + C_{n_{\delta_r}} \delta_r
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

a_x, a_y, a_z are the linear acceleration components.

In this case the actual time series of the aerodynamic coefficients are not directly obtained from the simulator, but calculated based on typical aircraft instrumentation. The instruments are in this case, assumed to provide noise and bias free perfect measurements. This does not mean that systematic errors are not included and simulations will demonstrate how the corrections affect the results. Table 4 shows the used aircraft sensors.

Table 4. Sensors used for obtained measurements

Sensor	Measured value	Description
Accelerometer	a_x, a_y, a_z	Acceleration in body coordinates.
Rate gyro	p, q, r	Angular velocity in body co- ordinates.
Alpha vane	α	Angle of attack sensor.
Beta vane	β	Measures the flank angle.
Pitot-static tube	Q	Measures dynamic pressure.
Aileron sensor	δ_a	Aileron deflection angle.
Elevator sensor	δ_e	Elevator deflection angle.
Rudder sensor	δ_r	Rudder deflection angle.

IMPLEMENTATION OF A REAL-TIME INTERFACE BETWEEN MICROSOFT FLIGHT SIMULATOR AND “THE REAL TIME WINDOWS TARGET” MODULE OF SIMULINK/MATLAB

We design our Software to interface the simulated aircraft in Flight Simulator environment (read and/or write many sensors, actuators data and parameters).

Figure 4:

Block diagram of the software environment design.

We communicate with FS2004 by using a dynamic link library called FSUIPC.dll (Flight Simulator Universal Inter Process Communication). This library created by Peter Dowson is downloadable from his website (www.schiratti.com/Dowson.html) [16], and can be installed by being copied in the directory (module) of FS2004. It allows external applications to read and write in and from Microsoft Flight Simulator MSFS by exploiting a mechanism for IPC (Inter-Process Communication) using a buffer of 64 Kb. The organization of this buffer is explained in the documentation given with FSUIPC, from which the Table II is taken.

To read or write a variable, we need to know its address in the table, its format and the necessary conversions. For example, the indicated air speed is read as a signed long S32 at the address 0x02BC.

Table 5. Flight parameters in the buffer FSUIPC

Adress	Name	Var.Type	Size (octet)	Usage
6010	Latitude (λ)	FLT64	8	Degree
6018	Longitude (μ)	FLT64	8	Degree
6020	Altitude (h)	FLT64	8	Meter
057C	Bank angle (ϕ)	S32	4	Degree
0578	Elevation angle (θ)	S32	4	Degree
0578	Head angle (ψ)	U32	4	Degree
30B0	Rotation rate (p)	FLT64	8	rad/s
30A8	Rotation rate (q)	FLT64	8	rad/s
30B8	Rotation rate (r)	FLT64	8	rad/s
3060	Acceleration (ax)	FLT64	8	ft/s ²
3068	Acceleration (ay)	FLT64	8	ft/s ²
3070	Acceleration (az)	FLT64	8	ft/s ²
0842	Vertical speed (Vz)	S16	2	meter/min
02BC	Speed IAS (V)	S32	4	Knot*128
2ED0	Incidence (α)	FLT64	8	Radian
2ED8	Incidence (β)	FLT64	8	Radian
0BB2	Elevator deflection (δe)	S16	2	-16383 to +16383
0BB6	Aileron deflection (δa)	S16	2	-16383 to +16383
0BBA	Rudder deflection (δr)	S16	2	-16383 to +16383
088C	Thrust control (δx)	S16	2	-16383 to +16383

Figure 6:

Rotation rates rd/s.

The estimation of the aerodynamic parameters is performed with TLSE method. Fig. 7 shows the measured and estimated values of the longitudinal force coefficient C_x , the vertical force C_z , and the pitching moment coefficient C_m .

Figure 7:

Measured and estimated aerodynamic coefficients

The Fig. 8 shows the measured and estimated values of the rolling moment coefficient C_l and the yawing moment coefficient C_n :

Measured and estimated aerodynamic coefficients.

Finally, the goodness of fit the model can be expressed in terms of a correlation coefficient between \underline{Y} and \underline{Y}_{est} . This coefficient is usually referred to as the multiple correlation coefficient whose square is:

$$R^2 = \frac{[\underline{Y}_{est} - \bar{Y}]^T [\underline{Y}_{est} - \bar{Y}]}{[\underline{Y} - \bar{Y}]^T [\underline{Y} - \bar{Y}]} ; \bar{Y} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N Y_{est}(i) \quad (18)$$

In general, the estimated values of C_{Xest} , C_{Zest} and C_{mest} fit well with the measured values. The total correlation coefficient R^2 , see equation (18), of the force and moment coefficients are 0.1337, 0.9777 and 0.927 respectively. The value of the multiple correlation coefficient R can be as high as one when the model fit is perfect, or zero when no correlation exists between the estimated and the measured dependent variable Y. The obtained results show that it is possible to identify at the same time the whole set of the aircraft aerodynamic coefficients derivatives by using the TLSE method (see Fig. 9).

Estimated aerodynamic coefficient derivatives

In this paper, procedures of the creation, the 3D modeling and the integration of an aircraft model in simulated environment have been explained. After that, the aircraft aerodynamic aspect for Microsoft Flight Simulator has been presented. Our approach uses the environment simulator (FS2004) to reduce the design process complexity. Particularly, we are interested in the flight tuning section in the “aircraft.cfg” file, which treats the aerodynamic part. In this section, we realize that the aerodynamic coefficients derivatives are unknown and not afford by MSFS 2004. The only provided numerical values (default 1 in most cases) are multipliers to the aerodynamic coefficients derivatives.

We have presented the Total Least Square Estimators Method (TLSE) applied to the aerodynamic identification problem. This method is based on the use of the SDV decomposition. It has the interesting propriety of giving the best approximation of the augmented measurement matrix, by another matrix with the same dimension, but with a lesser range, in the sense of the least squares.

The aerodynamic parameter in the model has been estimated based on flight data using the TLSE method. The parameters identification results show a good match between the estimated and measured values.

REFERENCES

- [1] Harkegard O. Flight Control Design Using Backstepping. LINKOPINGS UNIVERSITET, LINKOPING, SWEDEN, 2001.
- [2] Feldstein C.B., Muzio J.C. Development of a fault tolerant flight control system. 23RD DIGITAL AVIONICS SYSTEMS CONFERENCE IEEE, PP. 6.E.3 - 61-12 VOL.2, 2004.
- [3] Louali R., Belloula A., Djouadi M.S., Bouaziz S. Real-time characterization of Microsoft Flight Simulator 2004 for integration into Hardware In the Loop architecture. 19TH MEDITERRANEAN CONFERENCE ON CONTROL AND AUTOMATION (MED), PP. 1241-1246, 2011.
- [4] Microsoft Flight Simulator 2004 and FSX. <https://www.microsoft.com/enus/download/details.aspx?id=9727>, 2009.
- [5] Zaouche M., Beloula A., louali R., Bouaziz S., Hamerlain M. Adaptive differentiators via second order sliding mode for a fixed wing aircraft. COMPUTER MODELING IN ENGINEERING AND SCIENCES.VOL.104, NO.3, 2015.
- [6] Microsoft developer network. <https://msdn.microsoft.com/enus/library/cc526949.aspx>. MICROSOFT CORPORATION, 2008.
- [7] Klein V., Murphy P.C., Curry T.J., and Brandon J.M. Analysis of Wind Tunnel Longitudinal Static and Oscillatory Data of the F-16XL Aircraft. NASA/TM-97-206276, 1997.
- [8] Golub Gene H., Van Loan Charles FMatrix computations. 4TH EDITION, THE JOHNS HOPKINS UNIVERSITY PRESS BALTIMORE, . 2013.
- [9] Roskam Jan. Airplane flight dynamics and automatic flight controls, part I. DARCORPORATION, 2001.
- [10] Zaouche M. Identification et commande robuste d'un engin aérodynamique volant à 03 axes», THESE DOCTORAT, ECOLE MILITAIRE POLYTECHNIQUE, ALGIERS, 2015.
- [11] Zaouche M., Amini M., Foughali K., Aitkaid S., Bouchiha N.S. Application of the total least squares estimation method for an aircraft aerodynamic model identification. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MECHANICAL, AEROSPACE, INDUSTRIAL, MECHATRONICS AND MANUFACTURING ENGINEERING. VOL 10, N°06, PP.1067-1076, 2016.
- [12] Adiprawita W., A. S. Ahmad, J. Semibiring, Hardware In The Loop Simulator in UAV Rapid Development Life Cycle. ICIUS, BALI, INDONESIA, 2007.
- [13] Anderson John D. Aircraft performance and design», MCGARW-HILL, 1999.
- [14] Brandon Jay M. and Foster. John V. Recent dynamic measurements and considerations for aerodynamic modeling of fighter airplane configurations. AMERICAN INSTITUTE OF AERONAUTICS AND ASTRONAUTICS, AIAA - 98-4447, 1998.
- [15] Boiffier Jean-Luc. The dynamics of flight: The equations. JOHN WILEY AND SONS, 1998.
- [16] Dowson P. FSUIPC: Application interfacing module for Microsoft Flight Simulator. Available online at: www.schiratti.com/dowson.html, 2012.
- [17] Gimenes R., Castro Silva D., Paulo Reis L and Oliveira E. Flight simulation environments applied to agent-based autonomous UAVs. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON ENTERPRISE INFORMATION SYSTEMS, 2008.

- [18] Laban M. On-Line Aircraft Aerodynamic Model Identification. PHD DISSERTATION, TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELF, 1994.
- [19] Markovsky Ivan, Huffel Sabine Van. Overview of total least-squares methods. SIGNAL PROCESSING, SCIENCE DIRECT, 2007.